

A STUDY ON BANGALORE SCHOOL STUDENTS ANXIETY LEVEL

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Abstract:

Student's anxiety disorders may be caused by environmental factors, medical factors, family problems, financial problem, personal problem, etc., The main objective of the study is to identify reasons for school students anxiety in Bangalore. The study is based on primary data and 100 respondents were collected from various students in Bangalore using interview schedule method. The collected data has been analysed using simple percentage, ranking method, scaling technique, t test and ANOVA. It is found from the analysis, poor study habits was the first anxiety reason of the school students in Bangalore. To avoid these anxieties among school students proper guidance and counseling should be given to the needed students.

Key Words: School, Student, Anxiety, Problem, Factors, Education, Growth, Behavior, Etc.,

Introduction:

In India education plays an vital role in economic and social development of our nation. It is very important in building nation and it is the pre-requisite for the accomplishment of other development goals of our nation as well as for the individual. The scope of education is very wide and it is continuous process in every human life. Every student in the classroom situation, gets knowledge from the teachers and the text books But they get knowledge through latest technology such as online, websites, apps, you tubes, etc., Classroom education is a formal education whereas family, society, mass-media are the sources of giving informal education. Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru has defined "Education is that process which makes the learner productive, creative and make him ideal citizen."

Gurudev R. Tagore has defined "Education is that process which teaches the learner to eliminate errors and make him to search the truth successfully." According to Ravindranath Tagore, "The purpose of education is nothing less than the highest purpose of man. The fullest growth and freedom to enable to mind to find out that ultimate truth which emancipates us from the bondage of dust and gives us wealth not of things but of inner light, not of power but of love, making this truth its own and giving expression to it."

Anxiety is an emotion that signifies the presence of a danger among students that cannot be identified, or if identified, is not sufficiently threatening to justify the intensity of the emotion.

Types of Anxiety Symptoms:

- Academic Anxiety Symptom: Abnormal behaviour of a student shown at the beginning of any new academic task like procrastination in academic activities, worrying most of the time, perform poorly in school work, fail classes and withdraw from socializing with peers or pursuing activities that interest him/her.
- Anxiety from Subjects: Possessing negative attitude towards a particular subject or different subjects due to one or the other reason. Anxiety caused by it is called anxiety from subject.
- Anxiety from Examination: Introduction of schemes like continuous and comprehensive evaluation (CCE) may lead students towards severe anxiety sometimes. Anxiety caused due examination type (Formative & Summative) is called anxiety from examination.
- Anxiety from School Environment: Anxiety caused by prevailing school environment like stiff competition among students, role of school administrator (Authoritarian/Democratic) is called anxiety from school environment.
- Anxiety from Teachers: Teaching incompetency and partial attitude of teachers inside the classroom also provoke academic anxiety of students. Anxiety occurring due to this phenomenon is called anxiety caused by teachers.
- Anxiety from Poor Study Habits: Anxiety caused by study strategies applied by students in their daily academic learning process.

Review of Literature:

Revina Ann Mary, Gregory Marslin, Gregory Franklin and Caroline J. Sheeba (2014), analyzed the level of state anxiety among board exam attending school students in Tamil Nadu. In this study, a sample of 100 students containing 50 boys and 50 girls from 10th and 12th grades collected and anxiety are measured by Westside Test Anxiety Scale. The study founded that all board exam going students had increased level of

anxiety, which was higher among boys and 12th standard board exam going students. The study resulted demographic variables showed that students from nuclear families presented higher anxiety levels compared to their desired competitive group. The study concluded that the prevalence of state anxiety among board exam going students in Tamil Nadu support the recent attempt taken to improve student's academic performance in a healthier manner by appointing psychologists in all government schools.

Atieq Ul Rehman (2016), determined the various factors which has reviewed the related literature of academic anxiety to find out the factors which lead students towards severe academic anxiety. The study was exploratory type of research design and qualitative analysis was adopted for the study. The study founded that personal, familial, institutional, social & political factors were identified as potential threat to provoke severe academic anxiety among students. The study founded that various preventive measures are to students who suffer from severe academic anxiety available both non-clinically and clinically. The study founded that awareness should be created among students and it help their professional at the right time.

Husain Salilul Akareem & Syed Shahadat Hossain (2016) identified the demographic and background information of students that differentiate their perception about quality of higher education. The research was undertaken with a sample of 432 students was taken from five top private universities of Bangladesh to evaluate their perception toward dimensions of higher education. For analyzing the research Multinomial regression analysis was conducted to identify the characteristics of students which make their perception about quality of higher education dissimilar. The conclusion of the study results that status of students for scholarship, extracurricular activities, parents' education, age, previous result, and university they study in have a significant influence on perception about quality of higher education.

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify reasons for school student anxiety in Bangalore.
- To determine the Bangalore school students anxiety level.

Limitations:

- The statistical tools used to analyze the data have their own limitations.
- The result of the study is based upon the reasons expressed by the students of Bangalore
- All the drawbacks of primary data are applicable to this study.

Research Methodology:

Area of Study:

The research study was done in Bangalore.

Nature and Source of Data:

The study is based on primary data; primary data has been collected from various students in Bangalore using interview schedule method and the secondary data have been collected from related journals, magazines, websites and textbooks.

Statistical Tools Used for Study:

- Simple percentage
- Ranking method
- Scaling technique
- t test
- ANOVA

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Factors	No of Respondents n=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	58	58
Female	42	42
Standard		
10	32	32
11	30	30
12	38	38
Age		
15 Years	27	27
16 Years	29	29
17 Years	14	14
18 Years	30	30
Area of Residence		
Urban	67	67
Semi –Urban	33	33
Parent's Income(Annual)		

Up to Rs. 2,00,000	32	32
Above Rs.2,00,000	68	68
Type of Family		
Joint Family	48	48
Nuclear family	62	62

Inference:

The table 1 describes the demographic profile of students taken for the study. Out of 100 students were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (58%) of the respondents are male, (38%) of the respondents are studying 12 standard (30%) of the respondents age is 18, (67%) of the respondents belong to urban area, (68%) of the respondents belong to joint family , (58%) of the respondents parent’s annual income is above Rs. 2,00,000and (62%) of the respondents belong to nuclear family.

Ranking Method:

The respondents were asked to rank the reasons for their anxiety.

Table 2: Reasons for Anxiety

Reasons	Rank
Poor Study Habits	1
Worry (School , Exam, Subject)	2
Self Image	7
Financial Problem	3
Family Problems	4
Internet Facilities	5
Located Area	8
Health Issues	6

Inference:

It is found from the above table, poor study habits was the first anxiety reason of the school students in Bangalore, Worry (school , exam, subject) was the second anxiety reason, Financial problem was the third anxiety reason of the students, Family Problems was the fourth anxiety reason of the students, Internet Facilities was the fifth reason anxiety reason of the students, Health issues was the sixth anxiety reason of the students, Self image was the seventh anxiety reason of the students and Self image was the eighth anxiety reason of the students.

Scaling Technique:

Table 3: Level of Anxiety

Level of Anxiety	No of Respondents	Percentage
High	55	55
Medium	20	20
Low	25	25

Inference:

The above table shows that (55%) of the students level of anxiety, (20%) of the respondents level of anxiety is medium and (25%) of the respondents level of anxiety is low.

ANOVA and t-test:

Table 4: Relationship between Student’s Demographic Profile and Level of Anxiety

Variables	Statistical Test	Value	Result
Gender and level of anxiety	t-test	t=9.19	S
Age and level of anxiety	ANOVA	F=6.949	S
Standard and level of anxiety	ANOVA	F=14.37	S
Area of residence and level of anxiety	ANOVA	F=12.34	NS
Type of Family and level of anxiety	t-test	t=0.87	NS
Parent’s Income and level of anxiety	ANOVA	F=15.86	S

*significant at 5% percent level

Table 2 depicts there is a significant difference in the level of anxiety among different male and female student. There is a significant difference in level of anxiety among age groups of the student. There is a significant difference in the level of anxiety among different standards of the student. There is no significant difference in the level of anxiety among different area of residence of the student. There is no significant difference in the level of anxiety among student type of family. There is a significant difference in the level of anxiety among student parent’s income.

Conclusion:

On the basis of the findings of this research, it may be concluded that school students has different anxiety. It differs from student to student. The finding of the study shows that educational plays vital role in students life. It is found from the analysis, poor study habits was the first anxiety reason of the school students

in Bangalore. Many students will experience some form of anxiety or panic during this Covid 19 pandemic situation and also they get more anxiety at time of opening school because of having poor understanding of subjects, irregular reading habits and exam related fear. It is also found that school students from rural background, monetary and health issue are major cause for their anxiety. To avoid these anxieties among school students proper guidance and counseling should be given to the needed students.

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